

Studies on Biosurfactants Produced by Hydrocarbon Degrading Bacteria

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ABSTRACT

Petroleum hydrocarbons are the most frequently occurring environmental contaminants because of their extensive use, found in numerous aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. The present study is aimed in the study of biosurfactants and its role in hydrocarbon degradation. Twenty four bacterial isolates were isolated from soil samples collected from automobile workshops. These isolates were further screened for hydrocarbon degradation and biosurfactant production. After preliminary screening, nine isolates SA3, SA6, SA7, SA8, SA10, SA12, SA14, SA18 and SA19 were selected for further analysis. Four of the isolates were identified through biochemical screening tests, and all the nine isolates were assessed for biosurfactant production through three screening tests: drop collapsing test, oil spreading technique and emulsification index tests. These screening procedures confirmed that SA3 and SA19 are the efficient strains for biosurfactant production. The presence of glycolipid and rhamnolipid biosurfactants is further supported by the results of TLC, SDS PAGE and FTIR analysis. These two strains were identified through 16SrRNA gene sequencing. Thus the present study made an attempt to isolate biosurfactants from bacteria that can be applied for degrading the petroleum hydrocarbon pollutants deposited in aquatic, marine or terrestrial habitats.

Keyword: Glycolipids, Rhamnolipids, Biosurfactants, Orcinol, Hydrocarbon.

INTRODUCTION

The pollution of soil and water by industrial chemicals is a serious problem afflicting the modern world. Petroleum hydrocarbons are the most frequently occurring environmental contaminants because of their extensive use, in both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. Bacteria are particularly suitable for biodegradation application because of the wide variety of carbon sources or electron acceptors used by various strains [1, 2]. The main advantage of bioremediation is its flexibility in handling various composition waste types in both water and soil environments [3]. Petrophiles are very unique organisms that can naturally degrade large hydrocarbons and utilize them as a food source. Microorganisms degrade these compounds by using enzymes in their metabolism and can be useful in cleaning up contaminated sites. Petroleum hydrocarbon-degraders include *Yokenella* spp., *Alcaligenes* spp., *Roseomonas* spp., *Stenotrophomonas* spp., *Acinetobacter* spp., *Flavobacter* spp., *Corynebacterium* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., *Providencia* spp., *Sphingobacterium* spp., *Capnocytophaga* spp., *Moraxella* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., and *Bacillus* spp. [4, 5, 6].

Microorganisms produce surface active compounds either extracellularly or these compounds are attached to microbial cells [7]. The major classes of biosurfactants include glycolipids (Rhamnolipids, Trehalolipids, Sophrolipids), lipopeptides and lipoproteins, fatty acids, phospholipids, neutral lipids and polymeric biosurfactants [8]. Nowadays, biosurfactants are used in industries as a cosmetic and special chemical substances, food, pharmaceuticals, agriculture, cleansers, enhanced oil recovery and bioremediation of oil-contaminated sites. Diverse functional properties namely,

emulsification, wetting, foaming, cleansing, phase separation, surface activity and reduction in viscosity of crude oil, makes it feasible to utilize them for many application purposes [9].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of sample:

Soil samples were collected from four different mechanic workshops in Srivilliputtur and Sivakasi. Soil sample were collected from the ground surface to a depth of 10-20 cm from specific location within the workshops that had heavy spoilage of engine oil and transported to laboratory under sterile conditions.

Isolation and enumeration of bacterial strains:

The bacterial strains were isolated by the enrichment culture technique of the soil samples in minimal salt medium. Crude oil (5% w/v) was used as carbon source and incubated at 37°C on a rotator shaker (200 rpm) for 4 days. The bacterial colonies obtained were further purified on Luria- Bertani (LB) agar plates. [10].

Screening of Hydrocarbon Degrading Bacteria -Hydrocarbon utilization test:

The bacterial isolates were tested for their ability to utilize diesel oil (1% v/v) as sole source of carbon and energy for their growth. The overnight cultures of the bacterial isolates were kept for 24-48 hrs incubation at 37°C on mechanical shaker. Growth of the organisms was assayed at regular time intervals up to 15 days by measuring the optical density at 600nm [11].

Screening of Bio-surfactant Producing Organisms

Detection and Quantification of Biosurfactants

Oil spreading technique: Bacterial isolates was incubated in Mckeen medium on rotary shaker (150 rpm) for 3 days at 25°C. The culture suspension was screened for biosurfactant production by the oil spreading techniques [12, 13]. 30ml of distilled water was taken in the petri dish (25cm in diameter).

Drop collapsing test: This assay relies on the destabilization of liquid droplets by surfactants. The assay was performed in micro-titer plate incubated with oil and cultural supernatant. Biosurfactant-producing cultures giving flat drops were scored as positive (+). Those cultures that gave rounded drops were scored as negative (-) [14].

Emulsification index (E24): The E24 of culture samples was determined by adding 2 ml of diesel and 2 ml of the cell-free broth in test tube, vortexing at high speed for 2 minutes and allowed to stand for 24h [12, 13].

$$E = \frac{\text{Height of emulsion formed}}{\text{Total height of solution}} \times 100$$

Hemolytic activity

Biosurfactant productivity of a culture was assessed in Blood agar. Hemolytic activity however has been considered an unreliable criterion for the detection of biosurfactant activity [16].

Orcinol assay: The orcinol assay was used for quantification of biosurfactants with L-rhamnose as standard and the optical density measured at 421 nm [14]

Purification of Biosurfactants

Acetone precipitation: Cell free supernatant of the culture grown in minimal medium is mixed with ice-cold acetone to precipitate emulsifiers, which is further suspended in phosphate buffer. The mixture is incubated at 4°C for 15–20 hours to get the precipitate of emulsifier [15]. The emulsifier was further purified through dialysis.

Crystallization: Once, biosurfactant is precipitated/ extracted, it is re-dissolved in an organic solvent (glycolipids such as rhamnolipids are concentrated). Reaction is also coupled with a temperature reduction, which crystallizes the biosurfactant (rhamnolipid). Therefore, it becomes less soluble in solvents [9].

Chemical Analysis of Biosurfactants

Biosurfactants obtained by crystallisation was subjected to FTIR analysis.

16SRRNA GENE SEQUENCING: Ribosomal 16SrRNA gene was amplified in 50µl of reaction mixture containing the genomic DNA of the corresponding strain with the primer set 27F- AgA gTT TgA TCC TGG CTC Ag and 1492R – TAC ggT TAC CTT gTT ACg ACT T. The amplified PCR products was purified by QIA quick gel extraction kit protocol and run in agarose gel electrophoresis for 4 hour.

RESULTS

Twenty four bacterial isolates were isolated from the collected soil sample. These isolates were further screened for hydrocarbon degradation in Minimal salt medium and biosurfactant production through orcinol test. Rhamnose concentration was highest in SA12 and SA14. A low level of less than 1mg per 100ml was reported in SA16, SA17, SA20, SA22, SA23 (Fig. 1a & 1b). Maximum growth was observed on the fifth and sixth day of inoculation in minimal salt media and declined after six days. The strain SA12 showed maximum

growth during its fourth day of inoculation, whereas the strain SA19 and SA14 showed an increasing rate of growth up to eighth day of inoculation. The bacterial isolates SA7, SA10, SA18 showed maximum growth on the 6th day. (Fig. 2a&2b) Based on the results obtained, nine isolates SA3, SA6, SA7, SA8, SA10, SA12, SA14, SA18 and SA19 were selected for further analysis.

The nine isolates were further identified through morphology, biochemical characterization tests and identified as reported in strains SA3, SA6, SA7, SA8, SA10 and SA19 were identified. The strain SA3 and SA19 was identified through 16SrRNA analysis as *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Enterobacter cancerogenus*

The supernatant of the strains added to the diesel oil containing plates showed clear zone by displaying their ability to displace the oil thus indicating biosurfactant production. The level of oil spreading was reported in the strains *S.maltophilia* SA3 and *E.cancerogenus* SA19 shows ++ and +++ respectively in oil spreading efficiency test, all other strains shows +. All the nine selected bacterial strains showed clear zone by displaying their ability to displace the oil thus indicating biosurfactant production. *S.maltophilia* SA3 and *E.cancerogenus* SA19 formed the maximum zone size (4.5mm) in the drop collapsing test (Fig. 3). *S. maltophilia* SA3 and SA18 occupied the next level (3.5mm). SA14 showed the lowest level of collapse (0.8mm). The emulsification index was obtained in the range 6 to 33% as reported in Fig. 4. *S. maltophilia* SA3 and *E.cancerogenus* SA19 occupied the highest percentage and *Pseudomonas* sp and *E.cancerogenus* SA19 was the least. Hemolytic activity of the biosurfactants was also measured in blood agar plates and reported in strains SA12, SA18 and *E.cancerogenus* SA19 are α hemolysis, strains SA6 and SA14 are γ hemolysis, all other strains are β hemolysis.

The biosurfactants present in the *S. maltophilia* SA3 and *E. cancerogenus* SA19 isolates were precipitated and separated through acetone precipitation and partially purified through dialysis. The purified biosurfactants were crystallized and analyzed through FTIR. FTIR analysis of the biosurfactants isolated from *S. maltophilia* SA3 and *E. cancerogenus* SA19 were reported in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 respectively. FTIR spectrum of the biosurfactant isolated from bacterial strain *S. maltophilia* SA3. FTIR spectrum of biosurfactant from *S. maltophilia* SA3 was recorded with peaks in 2923.83 (CH₃), 2854.4 (CH₂), 2376.45 (P-H), 1404.08 (-CH) and 1116.71 (C-C). FTIR spectrum of the biosurfactant isolated from bacterial strain *E. cancerogenus* SA19. FTIR spectrum of biosurfactant from *E. cancerogenus* SA19 was recorded with peaks in 2925.81 (CH₃), 2854.45 (CH₂), 2376.14 (P-H), 1384.76 (C-H) and 1116.71 (C-C).

16SrRNA gene sequence of *S. maltophilia* SA3 and *E. cancerogenus* SA19 were submitted in NCBI and published with accession numbers KJ858503 and KJ858504 respectively.

Discussion

Biosurfactant producing microbes are isolated and screened from hydrocarbon degrading strain from soil or water samples contaminated with hydrophobic organic compounds like petroleum, refinery wastes etc., [16, 17, 18]. Two among 130 oil-degrading isolates strains were found to produce biosurfactants [19]. Hydrocarbon degradation test and orcinol

test are used to select the more efficient strain. Hydrocarbon utilization of the bacterial isolates is reported with optimal growth on 4th day and 6th day for majority of the isolates. Growth rate of *E. cancerogenus* SA19 is found to be slow and sustained increase even up to eighth day of inoculation. Similarly different patterns of degradation by 7 strains are reported as follows; SY21, SY22, SY23, and SY44 were higher in the second day, while the rates of SY42 and SY43 were higher in day 4, while in day 6, the highest degradation rate was shown by strain SY24 [19, 20, 21]. It can be concluded that different strains showed different pattern of growth in minimal salt agar media supplemented with diesel oil concentration depending upon their degradation and utilization capacity. As per previous reports [22, 23, 24] the present study is also recorded with more number of *Pseudomonas* spp. *S. maltophilia* SA3 and *E. cancerogenus* SA19 showed best results among the nine strains in oil spreading test, drop

collapsing test and emulsification index and hemolytic test. Blood agar hemolysis test is used as primary screening technique to check biosurfactant secretion and not all biosurfactants hemolytic activity [25]. Similar to our results, the strain DGEF03, 05, 07 showed the clear zone by being able to displace the oil around the colony indicating biosurfactant production [26]. Oil spreading technique is a reliable and rapid method to detect biosurfactant production by diverse microorganisms [27, 28, 29]. *Arthrobacter* sp. displaced oil with a clear zone oil-water surface, and it decreased proportionally with a decrease in concentration of the biosurfactant. [30]. Most of biosurfactants are different types of glycolipids; among them the rhamnose containing glycolipids produced by *Pseudomonas* spp. have been studied most extensively [31, 32]. Many studies reported the significance of using more than one screening tests for biosurfactant production [33, 34].

Fig. 1a Orcinol assay for bacterial isolates (SA1 to SA13). Fig. 1b Orcinol assay for bacterial isolates (SA14 to SA24)

Fig. 2a Hydrocarbon utilization test for bacterial isolates (SA3, SA6, SA7, SA8 and SA10)

Fig. 2b Hydrocarbon utilization test for bacterial isolates (SA12, SA14, SA18 and SA10)

Fig. 3 Drop collapsing test for nine bacterial strains

Fig. 4 Emulsification index for nine bacterial strains

Fig. 5 FTIR spectrum of the biosurfactant isolated from bacterial strain SA3

Fig. 6 FTIR spectrum of the biosurfactant isolated from bacterial strain SA19

FTIR analysis of biosurfactants produced from *S. maltophilia* SA3 and *E. cancerogenus* SA19 shows many absorption bands corresponding to carboxylic groups, ester, hydroxyl and alkene groups revealing the presence of biosurfactants in the form of glycoproteins and Rhamnolipids. Infrared (IR) has been used mostly to quantify complex mixtures of congeners based on the relatively broad IR absorption bands corresponding to various hydroxyl, ester, and carboxylic groups present in Rhamnolipids. Strong and broad bands of the hydroxyl group free (-OH) stretch due to hydrogen bonding were observed in the region A (3368 cm^{-1}). The presence of carboxylic acid functional group in the molecule was confirmed by the bending of the hydroxyl (O-H) of medium intensity bands in the region D (1455-1380 cm^{-1}). The aliphatic bonds CH₃, CH₂ and C-H stretching with strong bands are shown in region B and D (2925-2856 and 1455-1380 cm^{-1}). The carbonyl (C=O) stretching was found in the region C (1737 cm^{-1}) with strong intensity bands. Two other strong peaks between 1300 and 1033 in region E due to C-O stretch are characteristic of an ester functional group in the molecule. The peaks in the range of 1121-1033 cm^{-1} was also reported as C-O-C stretching in the rhamnose. [35, 36, 37].

CONCLUSION

Twenty four bacterial isolates were isolated from oil polluted soil samples. These isolates were screened for hydrocarbon degradation in minimal salt medium supplemented with diesel oil and biosurfactant production through orcinol test. These screening procedures confirmed that *S. maltophilia* SA3 and *E. cancerogenus* SA19 are the efficient strains for biosurfactant production. The presence of glycolipid and rhamnolipid biosurfactants is further supported by the results of FTIR analysis. Thus the present study made an attempt to isolate biosurfactants from bacteria that can be applied for degrading the petroleum hydrocarbon pollutants deposited in aquatic or terrestrial habitats.

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